

INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA INTERFAOL METODLARDAN FOYDALANISH

Sayfiddinova Noila Akbar qizi

2nd year student of Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

Abstract: *In this article, interactive methods (work in groups, SWOT analysis, brainstorming, aquarium, ladder, cognitive map, cluster, student in the role of a teacher, role-playing games, case-study, boomerang, conversation, discussion, leadership schools, oratory tournaments, In addition, the content of innovative pedagogical technologies used in the teaching of foreign languages, in particular, English, are discussed today.*

Key words: *Interactive, method, quality, pedagogic, English language*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7729593>

Interfaol consists of a set of scientific, technological, organizational, financial, commercial activities aimed at creating a new product, the purpose of which is to use and provide the accumulated knowledge, skills, technology and production tools for the large-scale production of this new product. Therefore, interactive in education is a set of scientific, technological, organizational, financial, commercial activities aimed at training new personnel, the purpose of which is to direct and provide the accumulated knowledge, skills, technology and production process to train new personnel for the national economy on a large scale.

Therefore, pedagogical innovation is any pedagogical innovation aimed at training a new product, i.e. personnel, specialist, the purpose of which is to ensure high efficiency of the process. If we take the daily pedagogical activity of a teacher, innovation is equivalent to any innovation that the pedagogue introduces into his activity and is aimed at improving and ensuring the effectiveness of education. In fact, any innovation serves as a factor that ensures the development of society. Accordingly, pedagogic innovation, on the one hand, is the basis for traditional teaching with a new perspective and ideas. Innovation in education takes strength from tradition, but changes the content and essence of the educational process in new ways. Consequently, the innovation fundamentally rebuilds and ensures the quality of education.

In the development of pedagogical technology, special attention is paid to its ability to be used by each teacher in his practical work. When the teacher uses the developed pedagogical technology in his pedagogical activity and concrete lesson process, on the one hand, he ensures the repeated application of the pedagogical technology, on the other hand, he provides the conditions for the achievement of the pedagogical goal, in particular, he ensures that each student acquires the specified amount of education based on the standard. Pedagogical technology makes it possible to diagnose the quality and levels of the educational process, to determine its criteria, to study it regularly, to monitor the indicators of pedagogical activity and the processes of its change. A set of multidisciplinary methods

has been used in foreign language learning since the 20s of the last century. It is based on the "Cleveland Plan". Its main principles are as follows:

Foreign languages are not acquired by simple mechanical memorization. Because knowing chettili is in fact organically and closely connected with the personal-intellectual characteristics of each individual. Therefore, it is necessary to create a language environment free from the obligation to repeat simple words and memorize them.

Language is a part of the national-ethnic culture, and it is considered a valuable value as an approximate part of it. Therefore, the process of learning a language is actually learning another national-ethnic culture, understanding and accepting it. Therefore, it is necessary to form a foreign language based on original national cultural concepts. Each lesson in the process of learning a foreign language should be built on the basis of only one focus, that is, the center. The student should focus on the material built on the basis of this center in each lesson.

In the process of teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to ensure that each type of language learning, i.e. reading, writing, pronunciation, listening, gives the same standard and volume. Usually, the considered multidisciplinary methods are based on providing the student with deep and comprehensive information about the language and culture of the country being studied. However, the unique limiting feature of this method is that even if basic knowledge is formed in it, this method cannot fully ensure the student's language freedom.

It has been a long time since the full use of information and communication capabilities in the process of teaching foreign languages. The possibilities of information and communication are developing very widely, and their entry into the educational process is becoming very active and rapid. Among them, you can list the following:

Effective use of multimedia in teaching English;

2) Implementation of interactive whiteboard capabilities in English language teaching;

3) Implementation and effective use of electronic resources in teaching English.

A competitive, competent pedagogue who meets the requirements of today's time should be able to perfectly know his specialty, be able to introduce innovations, work tirelessly on himself, at the same time be able to widely use information and communication technologies, know foreign languages and be able to regularly apply them to the teaching process.

Today, the main offer in the language market is formed according to the demand of the consumer. According to S.G. Ter-Minasova, a senior specialist in linguistics and foreign language teaching methods, "Today, language teaching has become more functional, and as a result of the strengthening of integration processes, the study of foreign languages, especially English, has become more relevant. But modern linguists are not interested in the history of language or its theory. English has become necessary for them to meet their life needs.

Currently, there are several methods offered to students learning English. One of them is the fundamental method. It requires at least 2-3 years of study and deep study of grammar. This method is mainly used in the training of professional translators, and at the end of their

studies, students will be able to see the world through the eyes of a native speaker. Based on it, language is studied as a real and complete means of communication.

Currently, the fundamental method has not changed its purpose, but many other methods have entered the field of competition with the fundamental method. One of them is the linguistic and sociocultural method. This method requires learning the language in a social and cultural environment. Its supporters condemn the fact that students are made to study "dead" lexical-grammatical forms. According to them, "a person is a product of culture." So the language too. In most cases, language is compatible with social life.

According to linguists, 52% of such errors are the direct transfer of phrases from the native language into English, and 44% are determined by the insufficient capacity of the language learner. The most important thing in the process of learning a language is how correct the content of the information is. Linguistic and sociocultural method covers two types of communication. It is language and intercultural communication. A student of a higher educational institution should not only acquire high levels of reading, writing and translation in English, but also learn to see English from the perspective of other people's culture. An English teacher should pay attention to these aspects in the process of language teaching. Another method of teaching a new language is the communicative method, which is effectively used today in Europe and the United States. As the name implies, this method is based on interaction, in which reading, writing, speaking and understanding the dialogues are important, which form the basis of any language learning training. Of course, in this method, teachers pay more attention to the last two methods (speaking and understanding dialogues), and in such lessons you will not encounter complex word devices and serious vocabulary. The disadvantage of this method is that a student who has a wealth of vocabulary in any field can easily understand the content of the text in this field, but it is difficult to enter into a serious dialogue with an expert in the field. The purpose of this method is, first of all, to overcome the fear of communication.

Therefore, in order to learn the language in depth and to start easy communication, it is necessary to teach English using the three methods listed above. In our opinion, it is necessary to teach the student to speak English first, and to think in this language at the second stage. It is a difficult but doable process. For this, the English language teacher should enrich the teaching method with various games, communication with peers, exercises on finding mistakes, comparative analysis of texts, etc., in addition to the standard approach.

REFERENCES

1. Nosirovna, M. M., & Musulmanovich, N. J. (2021). Dialect Words in the Works of Maksim Gorky. *International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences*.
2. 118).11.Musurmankulova, M. N., Boymirzayev, D. B., & Norbadalov, D. M. (2021). HISTORY OF COMPARATIVE DIALECT STUDIES. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES* (2767-3758),2(06), 55-66

3. Musurmankulova, M. N., Boymirzayev, D. B., & Norbadalov, D. M. (2021). HISTORY OF COMPARATIVE DIALECT STUDIES.CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES (2767-3758),2(06), 55-68

